
**TRANSLATION TRANSFORMATIONS AS A TOOL FOR
UNDERSTANDING THE LINGUISTIC VALUE OF WORDS AND
PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS**

Gulcharos Sotiboldiyeva

Teacher, Department of English Translation Theory,
Uzbekistan State University of World Languages.

gulcharos.muratovna@gmail.com

Abstract: This article analyzes various aspects of linguistic units and explains their specific features. The article examines the interaction of translation transformations with other modifications. The influence of complex translation transformations on the expression of the discursive form of the source text in translation is also considered. The problem of multi-interpretation of reverse translation has been studied, studying various aspects of inversion and its properties. The article also discusses the principles of connection between conversion and other translation changes. In addition, we analyze the impact of complex translation changes on the transmission of discursive forms of the original text. A number of our linguists have set a number of tasks for the study of lexicology, and the next task is the creation of a systematic dictionary of the Uzbek language. As an example, the article reveals the origin and current scope of neologisms in this work, as well as similar aspects.

Keywords: transformation, syntactic, lexicological, semantic, morphological, transliteration, English-Uzbek translation, translation, reverse translation, translation transformations, conversion, interpretation, speech form of the text, variant and invariant aspects of translation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada lingvistik birliklarning turli jihatlari tahlil qilinadi va ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari tushuntiriladi. Maqolada tarjima o'zgarishlarining boshqa modifikatsiyalar bilan o'zaro ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Tarjimada asl matnning diskursiv shaklini ifodalashda murakkab tarjima o'zgarishlarining ta'siri ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Teskari tarjimaning ko'p talqini muammosi o'rganildi, inversiyaning turli tomonlari va uning xususiyatlari o'rganildi. Maqolada, shuningdek, konvertatsiya va boshqa tarjima o'zgarishlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik tamoyillari muhokama qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, biz murakkab tarjima o'zgarishlarining asl matnning diskursiv shakllarining uzatilishiga ta'sirini tahlil qilamiz. Bir qator tilshunos olimlarimiz leksikologiya fanini o'rganish oldiga qator vazifalarni qo'ygan bo'lsa, navbatdagi vazifa o'zbek tilining tizimli lug'atini yaratishdir. Misol tariqasida maqolada ushbu asardagi neologizmlarning kelib chiqishi va hozirgi doirasi, shu kabi jihatlar ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: transformatsiya, sintaktik, leksikologik, semantik, morfologik, transliteratsiya, ingliz-o'zbek tarjima, tarjima, teskari tarjima, tarjima transformatsiyalari, konvertatsiya, talqin, matning nutq shakli, tarjimaning variant va invariant tomonlari.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются различные аспекты языковых единиц и объясняются их специфические особенности. В статье рассматривается взаимодействие переводческих трансформаций с другими модификациями. Также рассматривается влияние сложных переводческих трансформаций на выражение дискурсивной формы исходного текста в переводе. Изучена проблема мульти интерпретации обратной трансляции, изучения различных аспектов инверсии и ее свойств. Также в статье рассматриваются принципы связи конверсии и других изменений перевода. Кроме того, мы анализируем влияние сложных переводческих изменений на передачу дискурсивных форм оригинального текста. Ряд наших лингвистов поставили ряд задач по изучению лексикологии, и следующей задачей является создание систематического словаря узбекского языка. В качестве примера в статье раскрываются происхождение и современный объем неологизмов в данной работе, а также подобные аспекты.

Ключевые слова: трансформация, синтаксическая, лексикологическая, семантическая, морфологическая, транслитерация, англо-узбекский перевод, перевод, обратный перевод, переводческие трансформации, конверсия, интерпретация, речевая форма текста, вариантный и инвариантный аспекты перевода.

INTRODUCTION

The object of translation is not a language system as a type of abstraction, but a unique speech work in another language (original text), on the basis of which another speech work in another language (translation text) is created. The purpose of translation is to familiarize the reader (or listener) who does not know the original language with the given text (or the content of oral speech) as closely as possible. Translation is the correct and complete expression of something previously expressed in another language through one language. Achieving translation equivalence (translation adequacy), depending on the differences between the formal and semantic systems of two languages, requires, first of all, the production of a large number and quality of interlinguistic changes, that is, translation transformation. Studying the types and methods of translation transformation occupies one of the central places in the translation process. V.G. No, by translation transformation we mean abandoning the use of isomorphic means that exist in both languages. Implementation of translation changes can depend on various factors. The term

"transformation" is used figuratively in translation studies. In fact, we are talking about the relationship between the original and final language expressions, the replacement of one form of expression with another in the process of translation, which we figuratively call transformation or transformation.

Thus, the description of the following operations (translation transformations) are essentially cross-linguistic operations of "re-expression" of meaning. For ease of description, all types of changes made in the translation process can be reduced to four elementary types: replacement, substitution, addition, subtraction. But it should be noted that such a division is mostly approximate and conditional. First, in a number of cases, one or another transformation can be interpreted with equal success as a type of elementary transformation and as another type. Second, and most importantly, these four types of elementary translation changes rarely occur in their "pure form" in practice - usually, as the examples below show, they are combined with each other and have a complex character, "complex"

According to the scheme of V.G. Gak and Yu.I. Lwin, there are three types of equivalence: formal, semantic and situational. In formal equivalence, common meanings in two languages are expressed in similar language forms. In fact, all three categories of equivalence are the result of different translation operations: in the first case, it was about the simplest of operations - substitution, i.e. about replacing learned language signs instead of primary language signs, in the second and third - about more complex types of operations - translation changes.

METHODS

Within translation theory science, many translation scholars attach great importance to the study of transtranslation. [Komissarov V.N. 1973; Gorokhova A.I. 2004; Bruce E.V. 2007]. What is interesting about this phenomenon is that the nature of these translation corrections (changes) is very similar to the nature of antonym translations [Karabanova O.O. 2000; Garbovsky N.K. 2007]. When you use antonym translations and perform translation transformations, the grammatical and lexical levels of the language change simultaneously. At the same time, the nature of the transition takes on a deeper character, since lexical and grammatical substitutions and changes in the direction of action are also added to it. Usually, translation involves complex changes in translation, as they affect the semantic aspects of the text [Latyshev L. 1983, 317; Shechar A.D. 1988, 215]. In case of transformation, first of all, the semantic aspects of the situational image change. That is, the object of the sentence is described or described as if it were from the other side (other means of describing the same object are also used). Comparative literature, linguistic terms during the research for the article contrastive and descriptive translation and stylistic analyzes of artistic translation was studied. "Translation Theory" by I. Gafurov, O. Mominov, N. Kambarov, E. Ochilov's ``Issues of artistic translation``, ``Translation

by Gaybulla Salomov concerns`, J. K. Solijonov's graduation thesis, as a study guide and monographs were used. Lexicological and morphological problems were explained in the article.

RESULTS

This article is presented in the work selected as the object of translation using lexicological, morphological, syntactic transformations in sentences the problems encountered in the translation into the language are considered. In this work, literary creativity is interpreted as a separate type of activity, the meaning of which is to show people's actions, feelings, thoughts and various situations that take into account the world around them. Studying the types and methods of translation transformation occupies one of the central places in the translation process. By translation transformation we mean the abandonment of the use of isomorphic means that exist in both languages. The article emphasizes the need to study the process of disintegration of phraseological units during the translation process. Without knowledge and deep understanding of this process in the languages being compared, the translator is increasingly faced with the fact of "not being translated". It is very important that the phraseological changes in the translation reflect the national taste of the original language.

DISCUSSION

Literary creativity is interpreted as a separate type of activity, the meaning of which is to show people's actions, feelings, thoughts and various situations that take into account the world around them. "And that's why it's not a coincidence," V. G. Gak rightly points out, "in the literature of different peoples and different eras, similar plots, problems, and characters are often found". According to the most conservative estimates, there are at least thirty-three common plots in world literature.

The totality of land plots is determined as a result of borrowing, as well as simple coincidences of similar situations. One and the same deep plot can be developed with parallel development, borrowing, imitation, modifications, changes made to the existing plot. One of the genres that reflect the national-cultural identity of the society is the genre of fairy tales. It is known to many, for example, that it was simultaneously translated into French by Lafontaine, and then by I.A. Krylov - to Russian.

We are talking about the fairy tale "The Dragonfly and the Ant". Centuries later, the comparative analysis of Aesop's fable in Greek and Roman culture, and then its application to European culture, revealed various details related to the national-cultural identity of society. For example, in the first versions of the fairy tale, there were not cicadas and dragonflies, but beetles. Such a comparison of these options is well illustrated by VG Gak. When comparing French and Russian fairy tales, it is

noted that they are longer and wider than the source. The larger data content allows for the identification of characteristic features for each comparative culture. VG Gak notes three general differences from the prototype between Russian and French fairy tales - the choice of an animal, giving the characters a certain social status, and clarifying their reasoning and relationships. At the same time, he emphasizes the importance of "comparing the actions attributed to animals with their actual behavior".

In this regard, it is noteworthy that the famous entomologist J. Fabre even devoted an article to the tale of La Fontaine, which is aimed at determining the adequacy of the reflection of the biological aspect in the tale, i.e. lifestyle of insects, ways of living, living conditions.

V.G. Gak again reveals such serious differences between the two cultures (Russian and French): 1) the image of nature; 2) grammatical gender of the animal name; 3) a historical-cultural factor manifested in the nature of the relationship between the characters; 4) economic factor. To understand the above tale, the following is necessary. In France, cold comes with rain, and in Russia with snow. In French, "dragonfly" and "ant" are feminine words. They represent two women - there is no coincidence based on gender (equality), the absence of the slightest discriminatory motive. In the Russian text, "the ant is a man and is personified", as V. G. Gak humorously notes, a greedy and loving man refuses to help a poor, defenseless, beautiful woman in his own way. It does not cause a negative attitude towards the ant" [61. S.760-761]. V.G. In addition, Gak provides information on the very remarkable researches of Russian teachers, which identify the specific features of the Russian national character. Despite the simplicity and transparency of the idea of the parable, in the French text the relationship between the characters of the fairy tale is more formal and distant, they speak as "you". In the Russian version, the characters refer to each other as "you", and the relationship between them can be called less formal. In addition, at the same time, the characters use words accepted among close people (dear, gossip). In addition, "in the words of the ant, one can hear not so much anger towards the applicant, but the" cheerful cunning of the mind "and mockery, which Pushkin considered to be a characteristic feature of the heroes of Krylov" [61. S. 762].

Finally, the inconsistency between the two versions of the tale can be seen in the content of the request of the cicada and the dragonfly. The "French" cicada asks for a loan of grain with a promise to pay the debt and interest. And Krylov's dragonfly asks for "humanitarian help": "All this reflects a great sense of mutual help between Russian heroes, as well as, perhaps, a less developed level of commodity-money relations in the Russian environment of that time: we we are not talking about debt, but about free help" [61. P. 762]. As you can see, it is possible to get several moral

attitudes from only one fairy tale, which, apparently, creates a duality of perception, and the moral of the fairy tale and reflects the contradictions between the reader's impressions. As a result of his considerations, V.G. Gak draws a conclusion that reflects the specific features of the Russian person's thinking, a conclusion about the importance of the existence of not only national-cultural, but also universal human values: "We Krylov ant Russian reader We said that it does not create much sympathy among them. The same is true of the French ant, which readers tend to condemn. because they did not want to help their neighbor.. Both versions of the tale condemning thinking or idleness simultaneously condemn the lack of compassion"

CONCLUSION

The above example confirms that transformation transformations are complex. They are just grammatical, lexical and logical. It is incorrect to interpret this as change. As can be seen from the example, transformation transformation involves lexical, grammatical and logical changes simultaneously and affects all aspects of the linguistic form of a sentence. Unlike natural, purely grammatical transformations and antonymic translations, the level of influence of transformational transformations is more important in conveying the semantic content of the original text. These transformations are widely used in translation. Their use always requires movement to the rhetorical center of the sentence, the formation of a clear expression of the rhetorical center of the sentence and a direct transition. According to the analysis, the nature of translation transformation can be said to be complex and complicated. The stability of phraseological units does not always help to solve the problem of impact on the audience. The author tries to give the phraseological unit a different look, which is not very familiar to the reader or listener, to change its form. We consider such a violation of the integrity of a phraseological unit as a fragmentation of a phraseological unit. Any change in phraseology is reasonable and appropriate.

But one should not think that the change of a phraseological unit is only the result of replacing one component with another. This may be the result of other types of fragmentation of phraseological units, for example, dagger. The above indicates the need to study the process of disintegration of phraseological units in the theory of translation. If he does not know and deeply understand this process in both languages, the translator is more and more faced with the fact of not being translated. This article presents an understanding of the essence of translation as a process of interlingual transformation explained within the framework of what can be called a semantic-semantic model. Since the text is linguistic, in other words, a sequence of sign units, the semantic content (meaning) of these units and the whole text can and should be revealed by establishing connections between these units and what lies beyond them. that is, the relationship of sign units to each other. Therefore, the task of the translator is to understand the meaning of the source text and to express the same meaning

(more precisely, a system of meanings) in another language. In this case, interlingual transformation occurs, i.e. replacing one character system with another leads to inevitable semantic losses. The translator should keep them to a minimum

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